

WAYS TO IMPROVE TEACHING QUALITY

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Introduction

Teaching learning process is one of the important part of education process. Students' academic progress is also depend upon the active involvement of teacher and students. If the teachers are active, they can make students active. Teaching is one of those rare jobs in which one's work is wrapped up in one's personality. Teacher should update himself with new technologies and even he should improve quality of teaching by making use of various new pedagogies, cooperative strategies and teaching skills. Paper is highlighting on the various ways of improving teaching quality.

Teaching quality can be improved by following ways:

- By making use of Advanced pedagogy
- By making use of Co-operative strategies
- By making use of teaching skills

A)By making use of Advanced pedagogy

Advanced pedagogy means teachers can integrate different techniques, innovative teaching strategies, ICT tools, decision making tools etc into their teaching. Due to advanced pedagogy learning environment will be supportive and productive. It builds positive relationships through knowing and valuing each student. It helps to encourage students self confidence and willingness to take risks with their learning. It ensures students success through structured support & recognition of their work. It provides contemporary knowledge and practice to students.

Following advanced pedagogy can be used for effective teaching:

- **Problem based learning-** Problem based learning is defined as the learning that results from the process of working towards the understanding of a

resolution of a problem. The problem is encouraged first in the learning process. Problem based learning is very effective method for improving students' problem solving skills. Students actively work with information rather than passively receiving information and they make strong connection between concepts. PBL helps to develop confidence in problem solving and motivates them to become self directed learners. Positive relationship develops between teacher -students and student- student, it gives students ownership over their learning. It enhances students' motivation to learn and ability to achieve.

- **Field based learning-** in field based learning students learn through direct interaction with an environment which reflects taught concepts and ideas rather than learning through traditional ways of teaching like lectures or through textbook. Field based learning provides an opportunity to make use of non accessible matters which enables direct contact & interaction. It stimulates higher understanding of previously learned topic. It provides an opportunity to carry out various practice skills which can not be carried out elsewhere. Students value visited environment.
- **Active learning-** Active learning is a student centered approach in which the responsibility for learning is placed upon the student, mostly working in collaboration with their classmates. Role playing, case studies, debates, peer teaching etc. Are the techniques of active learning. Students are able to apply condition to a real world situation. The benefits of active learning is that it improves critical thinking skills, increased retention and transfer of new information, improves interpersonal relationship and increases motivation.
- **Situation based learning:** In situation based learning interactive situations are used, it support to active based learning such as problem based learning. Realistic situations are put up in front of the students. Environment for learning is well designed as students are made aware about predefined objectives and learning outcome so students work towards the objectives. Learner is given freedom of using available resources. Student have to

complete the situation, then he should do oral reflection of the situation and self assessment. So this type of learning make student self learner.

- **Teaching by Philp Jackon Model:** Philp Jackon Model is about three phases of teaching Pre-active phase, Interactive phase and Post active phase. In pre active phase activities which a teacher performs before entering the class room. it is planning of lesson which includes instructional objectives, methods of teaching, learning strategies, use of teaching aids, activities etc. interactive phase includes learning experiences, sizing of the class, knowing the learners etc. This phase is about execution of the plan. Post active phase is nothing but the evaluation or learning outcome of the students. Teaching learning process should go by these steps for improving the quality of teaching.
- **Field trips, tours and excursion:** Field trips, tours and excursion are part of active learning. visits for various geographical, historical places industries, training centres could be organized these tours could be in and around the city. It helps to know more about physical & social environment. Students get hands on experiment

B)By making use of Co-operative strategies:

- Cooperative learning is very effective learning strategy in which small teams work together. Where different level of ability of students use variety of activities to improve understanding of the subject.
- **Pair share:** In this strategy two students or students in small group are engaged in small group thinking before they put their answer or views in front of others. In pair or in small pairs they share their ideas, views, opinions with each other. So they are more active in thinking process and expressing her views. Students get chance to learn from their peers.
- **Jigsaw:** “The Jigsaw strategy is used to develop the skills and expertise needed to participate effectively in group activities. It focuses on listening, speaking, cooperation, reflection and problem solving skills.” Kal Hakkarainen

- **Brain storming:** Brainstorming is a process of generating new ideas. Brainstorming is of two types that is traditional and advanced brainstorming. Purpose of traditional brainstorming is to get maximum ideas from the group so in this type people sit in a group to think and give maximum ideas. Advanced brainstorming uses creative and lateral thinking. It produces more original ideas in more efficient way. Students feel more important part of education as their ideas are taken into consideration.
 - **Constructivism:** The purpose of leaning for an individual is to construct his own learning and not just recalling answers. It eliminates standardized curriculum and promotes curricula based on student's previous knowledge. In constructivism role of teacher is completely facilitator and he focus on making connection between facts and fosters new understanding in students. Students become more confident about their knowledge and understanding. Constructivism implies comprehensive learning through experience. It allows students to apply new knowledge in new context. This approach works with learners of all ages.
- C)By **making use of teaching skills-** Teacher can make use of following teaching skills in teaching learning process.
- **Visionary Approach-** A person who is ahead to his time and has definite courage and strong plan to change the future is called as visionary or who can think about the future advancements in creative and imaginative way is called as visionary person. Visionary teacher is optimistic about future. Such kind of teacher always think about the betterment of student's progress.
 - **Motivational behavior-** Motivation means one's direction to behavior. Teacher should motivate the students for study and advancement in knowledge. Teacher should create willingness among students to perform in the best of their abilities. Every child has some or other potential in him/her. If the child is motivated he can do miracles in his life.
 - **Life long learning-** Life long learning is self directed. Learner has continuous quest to seek formal, non formal or informal education. Due to lifelong

learning we get satisfaction, growth and financial benefits. Teacher should be lifelong learner and even he should motivate students for lifelong learning. Teacher increases his knowledge and he percolates his knowledge.

- **Positive thinking-** positive person can overcome any obstacle and difficulty. He gets happiness, success and health. Negative emotions narrow person's mind and he is not able to concentrate on his growth and unfortunately he doesn't get satisfaction. Due to negative mind student's growth stops so teacher should motivate the students to think positively.
- **Good planner-** Teacher should be good planner. Before entering the class he should plan for teaching methods and techniques, objectives should be fixed prior, teaching styles need to be given proper thought. Not only regarding the subject teacher should plan but also he think about the overall development of the students and by keeping this in mind he should plan co-curricular , extra curricular activities and think about skill development.
- **Impartial-** While dealing with the students teacher should be impartial means he should treat everyone equally. While teaching in the class, teacher should pay equal attention on every student, provide equal chance to interact in the class, to participate in various activities. Emotionally equally attached with everyone.
- **Knowledge of Technology-** Today's world is of technology. Students are more updated than teachers regarding making use of technology. To give updated knowledge of the subjects, he should have knowledge of technology. He should be able to make use of smart class, audio, video. OHP whenever required. Technology helps to create interest in teaching learning process
- **Need based teaching style** – Every individual is different from one another and so style of learning is also different. Some students can learn just by listening carefully which are called as audio learner. Some students need some or other teaching aids they are called as visual learner and some of them are kinesthetic learner who require audio visual things. As per the requirement of learner learning style should be used.

- **Diagnosis ability-** Teacher should have diagnosis ability. Purpose of diagnosis is to find out current state of a student's progress or ability in a particular area. Diagnosis ability helps to measure where students are in terms of their knowledge & skills. It helps to identify where students commit mistakes. It helps to plan remedial teaching as per the diagnosis and to achieve the desired goals of the education.

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